
Research Article

New combinations in *Koenigia* (Polygonaceae)

Rajeev Kumar Singh

Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, AllMS Road, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

*E-mail-id: rksbsiadsingh@gmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0136-9243>

Article Details: Received: 2025-03-30 | Accepted: 2025-07-22 | Available online: 2025-07-25

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Abstract: Seven new combinations are proposed here under the genus *Koenigia*. Additionally, the lectotype is designated for the name *Pleuropterypyrum mollifolium* Kitag.

Keywords: *Aconogonon*, China, Endemic, Kyrgyzstan, Myanmar, North Korea, *Pleuropterypyrum*, Russia, Tajikistan

Introduction

The genus *Koenigia* L. comprises about 54 species, distributed in the Northern Hemisphere (POWO, 2025). Presently, *Aconogonon* (Meisn.) Rchb. and *Pleuropterypyrum* H.Gross are synonymous to the genus *Koenigia* (Schuster et al., 2015). Therefore, seven validly published taxa previously placed under *Aconogonon* and *Pleuropterypyrum* are here transferred to *Koenigia*. Furthermore, a lectotype for the name *Pleuropterypyrum mollifolium* Kitag. is designated here in accordance with the guidelines and recommendations of Article 9 of the Shenzhen Code (Turland et al., 2018).

Now combinations

Koenigia brachytricha (Ohwi) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Polygonum brachytrichum* Ohwi, Acta Phytotax. Geobot. 7(3): 129. 1938. *Aconogonon brachytrichum* (Ohwi) Soják, Preslia 46(2): 151. 1974.

Holotype: North Korea, Komosan in Kampoku, 22 August 1933, G. Koidzumi s.n. (KYO).

Distribution: Korean Peninsula.

Figure 1: Holotype of *Pleuropteropyrum microcarpum* Kitag. (TI-02814, © Herbarium of University of Tokyo)

Figure 2: Lectotype of *Pleuropteropyrum mollifolium* Kitag. (TI-02817, © Herbarium of University of Tokyo)

Figure 3: Holotype of *Aconogonon rhombitepalum* S.P.Hong (E00314009, © Herbarium of Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh)

Koenigia microcarpa (Kitag.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Pleuropteropyrum microcarpum* Kitag., Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 50: 73. 1936. *Aconogonon microcarpum* (Kitag.) H.Hara, Fl. E. Himalaya 632. 1966.

Holotype: North Korea, Province Kan-nan, Fluvium Jalu super, Sam-su district, Vallis Onkolmuri, 8 August 1897, V.L. Komarov 564 (TI, Figure 1).

Distribution: Korean Peninsula.

Koenigia mollifolia (Kitag.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Pleuropteropyrum mollifolium* Kitag., Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 50: 75. 1936. *Aconogonon mollifolium* (Kitag.) H.Hara, Fl. E. Himalaya 632. 1966.

Lectotype (designated here): North Korea, Province Hei-nan, in monte Ro-rin-san, July 1916, *T. Mori* 15 (TI, Figure 2).

Remaining syntype: North Korea, Province Hei-nan, in monte Ro-rin-san, July 1916, *T. Mori* 14 (TI, Figure 2).

Distribution: Korean Peninsula.

Notes: In the protologue of *Pleuropteropyrum mollifolium* Kitag., two specimens were cited as types, one representing the flowering stage and the other the fruiting stage. To fix the application of the name, the fruiting specimen, *T. Mori* 15, is designated here as the lectotype.

Koenigia rhombitepala (S.P.Hong) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Aconogonon rhombitepalum* S.P.Hong, Notes Roy. Bot. Gard. Edinburgh 46(3): 361. 1990.

Holotype: Myanmar, N'Maikha-Salwin divide, western flank of Chimili, 26°23' N, 98°48' E, 11000 ft., September 1924, *G. Forrest* 25039 (E00314009!, Figure 3); isotypes BM000950655!, K000831133!, NY02649472!.

Distribution: China (Yunnan) and Myanmar.

Koenigia sajanensis (Stepanov) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Aconogonon sajanense* Stepanov, Vestn. Krasnoyarsk. Gosud. Agrar. Univ. 7: 125. 2015.

Holotype: Russia, Krasnoyarsk, Karatuzsky district, West Sayan, Taygish river near the Kubik locus, 5 July 2013, *N.V. Stepanov s.n.* (KRSU); isotype KRSU.

Distribution: Russia (Siberia, Krasnoyarsk).

Koenigia zakirovii (Czevr.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

Figure 4: Type of *Polygonum zakirovii* Czevr. (TASH000779, © National Herbarium of Uzbekistan, Tashkent)

Figure 5: Type of *Polygonum zaravschanicum* Zakirov (TASH000781, © National Herbarium of Uzbekistan, Tashkent)

≡ *Polygonum zakirovii* Czevr., Ecol.-Biol. Osobenn. Vazhn. Cyreb. Rast. Cult. 181. 1978. *Aconogonon zakirovii* (Czevr.) Tzvelev, Novosti Sist. Vyssh. Rast. 29: 62. 1993.

Type: Kyrgyzstan (TASH000779!), Figure 4).

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan.

Koenigia zaravschanica (Zakirov) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Polygonum zaravschanicum* Zakirov, Bot. Mater. Gerb. Bot. Inst. Komarova Akad. Nauk S.S.S.R. 13: 38. 1950. *Aconogonon zaravschanicum* (Zakirov) Soják, Preslia 46(2): 151. 1974.

Type: Tajikistan (TASH000781!), Figure 5).

Distribution: Tajikistan.

Acknowledgements

The author is thankful to the Director, Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata, and Head of Office, Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, Jodhpur, for the facilities. I am also grateful to the curators of E, TASH, and TI for the images and information on type specimens.

References

- POWO. (2025). Plants of the World Online. Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. Available at: <http://www.plantsoftheworldonline.org/> (accessed 21 March 2025).
- Schuster TM, Reveal JL, Bayly MJ and Kron KA. (2015). An updated molecular phylogeny of Polygonoideae (Polygonaceae): relationships of *Oxygonum*, *Pteroxygonum*, and *Rumex*, and a new circumscription of *Koenigia*. *Taxon*. 64: 1188-1208. <http://dx.doi.org/10.12705/646.5>
- Turland NJ, Wiersema JH, Barrie FR, Greuter W, Hawksworth DL, Herendeen PS, Knapp S, Kusber WH, Li DZ, Marhold K, May TW, McNeill J, Monro AM, Prado J, Price MJ and Smith GF. (2018). International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Shenzhen Code). *Regnum Vegetabile*. 159. Koeltz Botanical Books, Glashütten. <https://doi.org/10.12705/Code.2018>